

Digital Marketing And Technology Innovation On Tourism Business Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 08, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 09, 2021</p> <p>Keywords: Digital Marketing, Innovation, Tourism Business, Thailand</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4918302</p>	<p><i>The study is carried out to examine the impact of the digital marketing on the business performance of tourism. Meanwhile, the study has examined the mediating role of technological innovation in the relationship between the digital marketing and the business performance of tourism. The study has used the survey-based methodology and SEM-PLS is used for the data analysis. The findings of the study offer interesting insights. The ability of digital marketing to keep effective track of their businesses has led its position prior to the traditional marketing. Any course of action intended to achieve its goal is when started can keep a track record of its extension, associations and transformations. It has enabled the researchers to investigate customers' needs and wants in a meaningful and in an innovative way. These arguments suggest that, by indulging digital marketing in the set of marketing strategies would make a huge contribution towards the effective attainment of business goals and objectives by making brands capable of getting deeper insights about customer choices and serving them better about it.</i></p>

Introduction

The dimensions of marketing have been experiencing drastic changes as the internet technology has stepped in the field. The consumers' way to see a brand have been elevated by the usage of internet. The traditional marketing strategies which have become obsolete are being totally modified by this technological advancement and it has changed every phenomena involved in marketing. Marketers do not believe in working with the older strategies as those are not sustainable anymore (Vries, Gensler, & Leeflang, 2017). Businesses running all over the world are more attentive towards digital marketing (DGM). Besides being an important tool of effective communication and a supplemental source of income for the firm, it plays its vital role in maintaining the relationships in the long-run with different groups of the market. Internet grasps "Interaction" as the main element to be taken advantage of, is making marketers capable of keeping connection with various parties (Kaur, 2017). Internet is not only the source of communication for users these days, but it also takes them to a next level for interacting with their favorite brands. Due to the linkage of internet with markets, the users are now capable of direct dealing their requirements with their preferred brands.

DGM can be comprehended as using different electronic platforms in order to place the promotion of products and services of a particular brand. It contrasts with traditional marketing strategies from the perspective of usage of various mechanisms in order to keenly understand the marketing campaigns and analyzing the successful and unsuccessful measures actually. (Source: sas.com) The approach used by traditional marketing in order to comprehend the customer details, is to first gather the data and then develop an analysis of it to get insights of the audiences. Internet advancements provides a deeper insights of the audiences and determines their behaviors prevailing throughout the electronic platforms (Kaur, 2017).The information gathered by digital means have altered the basis of decision making for the businesses. The steps taken by the marketers for achieving their targets, can frequently be checked and studied along with serving the customers based on their customized choices.

DGM is thought to be an evolved form of marketing in future as it encompasses new domain and has a high growth ratio, and it is changing the ways of travelers, while travelling, to build up a connection with travel destinations. Inversini (2017)discusses that, consumers and business can create a stronger link by using mobile phone technology leading towards a greater experience of customization. Applications related to tourism with the rise of internet are becoming the basic source of getting a new and vast circle of customers and expansion of business. People share their travelling stories and experiences on social media networks such as Facebook and Instagram, which play a vital role in the "Old mouth to mouth" promotion for tourism industry. Permatasari, Mapuasari, and Yuliana (2020), suggested that Digital form of marketing affects the relationship between customer and brands significantly. Zero moment of truth, referred as it is not only about purchasing decisions

but has been narrowed down to the important points of competition in the market in order to gain more and more attention of the customer (Permatasari et al., 2020). If discussing about the taste of tourism, this new generation has different priorities than the priorities of their parents and grandparents (Cavagnaro, Staffieri, & Postma, 2018). The frequency and expertise in mobile phone and internet usage of the young generation can play its part to give a significant boost to Portugal, Focusing the opinion of (Marlina, Hermawan, & Herawan, 2020), for the sake of tourism, this younger generation must be kept as an asset and it should be prioritized. The future of tourist is not like having a traditional old approach of capturing natives and adopting an obsolete style and thoughts, but the future holds to someone who contributes to tourism by using advanced technologies and a totally a new mindset. The ideas and behaviors of this generation are quite different and they should be prioritized for the development of the tourism industry (Marlina et al., 2020)

1.0. Literature Review

About a century ago, Marketing started to grow its footsteps and then related itself to the field of Economics. There are several ways to define Marketing as it started in 20th century and kept evolving with the passage of time under the influence of different environmental factors. But the question which arises first in mind is, what is the importance of the definition? One reason behind its importance is that it provides the limitations and sets the boundaries and describes the essential features. Moreover, the definition provides the opportunity to marketers and researchers by contrasting about what a standardized marketing actually is (Pasquier & Villeneuve, 2018). According to the suggestion of Pasquier and Villeneuve (2018), there is a strong effect on concepts of marketing by observing its impacts on consumer, organization and society. There has been a continuous effort putting by American Marketing Association (1973) in order to develop a generalized definition of marketing since last 70 years. The more realistic and actual definition was put forward by American Marketing Association in 2017 was: "Marketing is the activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large."

It is evident that, Internet has changed the dimensions of marketing throughout the globe and has eradicated the old and obsolete practices (Kaur, 2017). In order to excel in marketing, firms started considering DGM as the one of the most important tool (Kaur, 2017). He further argues that internet has enabled us for directly connecting with our favorite brands, besides connecting with the users, and by following this phenomena, a lot of opportunities have been created to make terms better with the stakeholders. In this Digital era, the frequently and wide use of smartphones and a wide variety of electronic applications have eradicated all the hurdles in the way of communication and has made it limitless (Cunha, 2019). No tourist now gets worried about the place and time while going for tourism because of these instantly usable applications (Cunha, 2019). Tourists in this digital age, do not bother about travelling hurdles because of taking the advantage of convenience provided by all-time available smartphones and applications systems for a random search (Cunha, 2019), for occupancy bookings and easy payment of reservations (Cunha, 2019) and keep going around their destination points (Cunha, 2019). Success of Tourism industry, along with other marketing strategies, is now also depending upon the digital advancement. Tourists and customers take reviews and feedbacks from digital platforms, their thoughts and decisions are highly impacted due to the level of trust they create in their mind (Alford & Jones, 2020). Stakeholders theory is put forward by Alford and Jones (2020), as a modern dimension for online business. They affirm that, when a customer purchases a product online, they are likely to be more trusting on that brand which treats their information efficiently.

Tourism plays a main role in exploration of historical and natural treasures and thus, is an important economy-supporting activity. Many countries have opened their boundaries and extended them for tourism which also results in social and economic development through creating employment opportunities, establishment of several start-ups and infrastructure. The international tourism and its extension have been driven from developed societies of the world, developing economies, new and advanced technologies and new forms of business and had elevated it to 5% in 2018 ("Int. Tour. Highlights, 2019 Ed.," 2019). This milestone was achieved after two years of UNWTO forecast. At the same time, the earnings generated from export sources by tourism grew up to USD 1.7 trillion. This means that tourism is the source of better economic conditions for any country which is responsible for creation of more and more employment opportunities and is the main support for innovativeness and entrepreneurial activities. In other words, tourism plays a vital role in the development of different regions and making the lives better and in changing the direction of communities towards modernization. Due to the fast-growing tourism, both developed and developing economies are benefitting from this with a significant rise in revenues. Tourism export is continuously rising since last 7 years and it is proving to be very helpful in reducing the trade deficit. However, as the tourism increases, there should also be an increase in the sense of responsibility that the enablers should be considerate about the effective destination management. Maintaining the sustainability with tourism is a greater challenge ever faced. Increase in volume is not enough but we also need to evolve for giving an adequate quality and value. Tourism sector is expected to be shape up by the involvement of innovation, use of digital access and changes in the mindsets of society. The organizations and

the tourists' destinations are supposed to remain competitive and to adopt tourism as a major source of Sustainable development and contributing to a bright future ("Int. Tour. Highlights, 2019 Ed.," 2019).

2.0. Hypothesis

Lim and Ok (2021) hypothesizes to measure the extent of tourism in three scopes: financial (e.g. RevPar), operational (e.g. occupancy or repeat visit) and organizational (e.g. customer satisfaction). This study treats Revpar and room occupancy as a dependent variable, which represents quality of bookings (Financial) and quantity of bookings (Operational) from a particular perspective respectively (Casais et al., 2020). To know how much effect is shown by DGM strategies and volume and valence reviews have upon the two KPIs (Park et al., 2020). In the present study it will be keenly analyzed that to which extent the tourism performance indicators hold the impact of driving elements of managerial and online reviews. Figure.1. demonstrates the research framework. Using a blend of survey method, online review data and analysis of tourism websites, the data was gathered from 132 tourists from the 5 tourism destinations of Flanders, Belgium. This study claims to provide different points of understanding about the working of tourism marketing and how to evolve and elevate the practice of marketing strategies in tourism. Lim and Ok (2021) differentiates the external and internal factors which might determine the performance of tourism.

Although the previous studies have focused the external factors which affected the behaviors and attitudes of consumers but this study focuses on both of the elements as recent studies have less exposure to the effect of online reviews over tourism performance. The contemporary studies also lack the evidences about the impact of internal factors upon tourism performance such as DGM strategies (Lim & Ok, 2021). Discussing and analyzing these two internal and external factors simultaneously would help the tourism industry to understand the influence of DGM strategies over tourism performance with the examination of mediating role of volume and valence reviews. The present study contributes in terms of the above explained relationships regarding different types of tourism which is a crucial topic for research and has been ignored till yet (Lim & Ok, 2021).

Our findings would help the marketing managers to develop a know how about the mechanisms of DGM strategies and which strategy to be focused for greater extent of its application, the expectations which they should expect from these strategies to be influential on the tourism performance indicators and regarding this procedure, what factors of online review should be considered and to be kept under observation.

One of the most important characteristics is the quantity of reviews which are gotten by the customers about a particular product or service. It has been suggested by the previous studies that higher the number of the reviews, would result in better performance of the business (Sharma & Nayak, 2020). Casais et al. (2020) report that the number of reviews have a positive and direct relationship with tourism bookings done online. Lim and Ok (2021) found out that the relationship between number of reviews and revenues generated through tourism is significantly positive. Casais et al. (2020) gave the evidence that Room occupancy, Revpar and number of reviews share a direct relationship among them. Sharma and Nayak (2020) says that decrement in room occupancy has the positive relationship with number of reviews regardless the review score. Through different arguments such as customers' negative or positive reviews create an image in their mindsets, give the product a familiarity with the people, information seekers are attracted and there is a process of mitigation of uncertainty and risks, it can be concluded that, review volume has a significant positive relationship with business performance (Gao et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2021). This argument leads us to the fact that popularity is prioritized and is given too much preferences (Sharma & Nayak, 2020). In addition to it, Casais et al. (2020) suggest that with an overwhelming reviews we can cancel the effect of those reviews which show extreme perceptions. A large number of studies has explained that business performance is affected by valence of online reviews.

Previous studies have not given sufficient attention to the influence of DGM strategies on tourism performance through its impact on online reviews. Pelsmacker et al. (2018) found out that the tourism managers should establish a DGM plan relevant to tourism and ensure their presence over the online platforms. Two main constituents are differentiated relevant to DGM plan. Firstly, in the field of tourism, one can use the digital information in many ways while making marketing efforts, for example, using the information present on the review sites, creating a linkage with the third-party on the website, or having a track record of Online travel agent's website reviews. Second, tourism managers can encourage the consumers and customers to indulge themselves into a direct conversation, for instance, by encouraging them to frequently comment. Previous researches have exposed the different elements of DGM plan and these are discussed here. One of the force having a higher impact on tourism industry is the usage of Information technology. González and Bulchand (2016) found out on the basis of in-depth interviews held with 30 tourism managers and extracted different ways through which IT can boost tourism performance and further suggested that there should be researchers to conduct the study which would focus upon clearing the issue that how IT can contribute more into this field. With the help of online feedbacks, managers can enable themselves to maintain the record of changing opinions and behaviors of the guests and rise or decrement in their satisfaction level. It can enable the management as well to take prompt decisions, and taking beneficial actions which might include the investment decisions according to the wants of customers, replying to their feedbacks and planning positive activities.

Pelsmacker et al. (2018) affirms the point that a successful response strategy is the one, which is positive and a customized response which takes lesser time. Sarro, Harman, and Zhang (2018) reported on the basis of an experimental research study conducted with the students that, showing affinity in the exchange of a negative review would certainly increase online rankings and ratings. If the response made was personal instead of a general response, it was rated more positively. While giving responses to the customers, managers should be considerate about the thought that the response is particularly given in accordance with the problem, and not a general statement to be given every time. Sarro et al. (2018) study suggests while contrasting with the other studies that, maintenance of fast responses given to the customers did not have any stronger influence over the ratings. The reason behind this argument may be explained as those are the potential customers instead of complaining customers, who do not prioritize time saving. Overall, the previous studies were more concerned about the effect of digital strategies on reviews. Nevertheless, Sarro et al. (2018) discuss, many studies and research were customer-oriented, and more concerned about the decision making of customers and their satisfaction elements and their trust, but now there is a fascination in studying about the factors which determine the online reviews and its effect on the performance of the business. Park et al. (2020) argue, that a gap has been left unfilled by the previous studies which is about the influencing factors affecting room occupancy and RevPar and how online generated reviews explicate them. In the present study, we are exploring the effects of 10 aspects of DGM strategy on online reviews which would finally show the effect on tourism performance. We predict that all the 10 aspects would keep a positive influence.

In the management domain, innovation is said to be a universal term as it is relevant to many concepts. Frequently, it tends to be portrayed as an "iterative cycle" started by the impression of another market opportunity for an innovation which prompts the turn of events related to development, production and marketing (OECD, 1991). The opportunities which are to be exploited might involve the new styles and techniques of production, idea development regarding new and innovative products, new tricks to manage businesses and entrance in the new markets, and the establishment of new techniques and procedures for enabling themselves and to come up with higher creativity level (Lin, Yip, & Sambasivan, 2020). The digital technology and its advancement have diverted the focus of the researchers and their conducted studies in the field of economics, marketing, management and engineering of production. In order to understand technological innovation, it is referred that a continuous and increased usage of technology in production phase and processing the business activities such as administration (Hervas, Sempere, & Boronat, 2021). According to resource-based view, any process indulging innovation and are having certain innovation capabilities are one of the most important capacities which could lead to successful strategic success. Innovations make the firm capable of achieving rareness, and the higher extent of inimitability, higher level of value creation which can boost up the organizational performance (Caloghirou, Giotopoulos, & Kontolaimou, 2020; Du, Zheng, & Chang, 2020). Thus, in the field of engineering as well as applied sciences, innovation plays a critical role to get break-through inventions. Concluding from this argument, we can say that a firm can be highly dependent on innovative capabilities in order to gain competitive edge in the industry (Lin, Ho, & Sambasivan, 2020). Due to these results of different researches, now firms are more inclined to invest in R&D departments in order to bring more innovation (Lin, Ho, et al., 2020), which would ultimately be increasing the competitive advantage of that organization. But, it should be taken in consideration that, technological adoption should be checked and matched in accordance with the desired economic gains for the organization and stakeholders as well. Firms rely on information technology to a greater extent in order to provide innovative products and services to the customers. Discussing the opposite perspective of using IT, that if investment in information technology does not provide enough edge to the organization, it would be considered as sunk cost because it won't boost up the organizational performance (Henstra, Jansma, & Swart, 2017; Hervas et al., 2021). On the basis of this argument, we can say that, there are many factors which support the relationship between organizational performance and Information Technology. The first factor is that the investment done in technology for the sake of innovation, which are influenced by the resources of that firm. The second factor may be, that the type of innovation and its sustainability level to support the business operations of the organization put forward by R&D department. Third factor is the extent to which the firm is adopting the technological innovation and is in which stage, whether in infancy stage, adopter stage or lagged, and its power of negotiation with its consumers and suppliers which would enable it to survive in market with a good competitive advantage. The fourth factor is, the new and advanced strategies to handle a product which are inimitable and rare and are not easily available in the market which would help in the production and dispersion of innovativeness in the market. The studies and different researches claim that the competitors would gain the competitive advantage through an open competition if the firm is not capable of gaining the competitive advantage from its own innovation process (Henstra et al., 2017; Hervas et al., 2021). In order to avoid this hurdle, organizations are inclined to invest the earnings earned from innovation in constructing and establishing new strategies to be employed in order to gain maximum competitive advantage (Junejo & Kalhor, 2020). The performance of the organization is mainly influenced by the strategies which are meant to be rare and innovative so it can be deduced that there is a

significant relationship between firm's performance and technological innovation (Caloghirou et al., 2020; Du et al., 2020; Hervas et al., 2021). On the basis of these provided literature arguments, we can propose that;

H1: Digital marketing (DGM) has significant impact on the tourism performance (TP).

H2: Technology innovation (TECHIN) has significant impact on the tourism performance (TP).

H3: Digital marketing (DGM) has significant impact on the technology innovation (TECHIN).

H4: Technology innovation (TECHIN) mediates the relationship between digital marketing (DGM) and tourism performance (TP).

3.0. Methodology

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A questionnaire survey was conducted by distributing questionnaires among the respondents. A total of 460 questionnaires were distributed. The non-response bias, sampling, and oversampling can be reduced through oversampling (Hair et al., 2016). For this reason, oversampling has been done to reduce the chances of non-response bias. Further, the results are expected to be reliable with the use of large sample size (Henseler et al., 2016). The minimum acceptable level of response rate has been set at 50% in research surveys (Hair, Matthews, Matthews, & Sarstedt, 2017). For data analysis, both descriptive and inferential statistics were adopted in this research study. PLS-SEM, a second-generation structural equation modeling, has been used because of its ability to determine multiple cause-and-effect relationships (Ramayah et al., 2018). It is an important tool for developing models and forecasting associations among variables (Ong & Puteh, 2017). To develop the structural and measurement model, Smart-PLS path modeling was used.

4.0. Results

A two-step process has been used for determining the results through the PLS-SEM approach, which includes the determination of measurement model and structural model ((Hair et al., 2016; Henseler et al., 2016).

Figure 1: Measurement Model

Table 1: Outer Loadings

	DGM	TECHIN	TP
DGM2	0.897		
DGM3	0.900		
DGM4	0.898		
DGM5	0.913		
DGM6	0.892		
P1		0.896	
P10		0.895	
P11		0.733	
P12		0.774	
P2		0.861	
P3		0.875	

P5		0.883	
P6		0.806	
P8		0.886	
P9		0.879	
TCHIN1			0.906
TECHIN2			0.854
TECHIN3			0.915
TECHIN4			0.894
TECHIN5			0.911
TECHIN6			0.858
TECHIN7			0.822
TECHIN8			0.863

In order to ensure whether the model has internal consistency or not, the composite reliability coefficient has been determined. The composite reliability coefficient has been selected because of equal contribution assumption in Cronbach's alpha by all the items to the construct. The value of Cronbach's alpha does not consider the individual role of loadings (Henseler et al., 2016; Akter et al., 2017; Hair et al., 2017). A conventional rule was put forward by Ong and Puteh (2017) for the interpreting internal consistency reliability and coefficient of composite reliability. It was suggested by Ramayah et al., (2018) that standard composite reliability value is equal or greater than 0.70. The composite reliability coefficients for all variables have been depicted in Table. The value of coefficient for every construct lies within 0.774-0.894. Thus, it is clear that all the values are above the standard acceptable value, which ensures internal consistency reliability of the constructs

Table 2: Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	CR	(AVE)
DGM	0.941	0.942	0.955	0.810
TECHIN	0.958	0.958	0.964	0.772
TP	0.957	0.959	0.963	0.723

The degree with which an item is linked with the measures of a construct is known as convergent validity ((Hair et al., 2016; Henseler et al., 2016). The value of items loadings related to the variable greater than 0.5 is considered as convergent validity. Three principles can be used for determining convergent validity. A significance level is possessed by all the indicators of factor loadings, as suggested by these principles. According to the second rule, the standard acceptable composite reliability value is above 0.7 and the standard acceptable value of AVE is above 0.5.

Table 3: Validity

	DGM	TECHIN	TP
DGM	0.900		
TECHIN	0.806	0.879	
TP	0.712	0.784	0.850

The differentiation level of a variable from another variable is another criterion, which is known as discriminant validity (Bryne, 2010; Hair et al., 2010). The AVE square root value has been used to determine the presence of discriminant validity. It is required that AVE square root value should be greater than the correlation between the variables (Hair et al., 2016; Henseler et al., 2016). Therefore, the AVE square root value was compared with the correlation value. The standard value proposed by Henseler et al. (2016) was adopted for determining discriminant validity, i.e. comparing the items of cross loadings.

This research has also determined the structural or inner model. For this, the bootstrapping method with 5000 bootstraps have been used for analyzing the significance of path coefficients (Hair et al., 2016; Henseler et al., 2016; Ong & Puteh, 2017)).

Figure 2: Structural Model
Table 4: Direct relationships

	(O)	(M)	(STDEV)	(O/STDEV)	P Values
DGM -> TECHIN	0.906	0.906	0.018	50.546	0.000
DGM -> TP	0.512	0.515	0.071	7.180	0.000
TECHIN -> TP	0.674	0.680	0.138	4.867	0.000

Table 5: Mediation

	(O)	(M)	(STDEV)	(O/STDEV)	P Values
DGM -> TECHIN -> TP	0.611	0.617	0.129	4.751	0.000

The determination of R-square is another criterion for determining the structural model. The R-square value is referred to as the coefficient of determination ((Hair et al., 2016; Henseler et al., 2016; Ong & Puteh, 2017). The total variations in the endogenous variable explained by exogenous variables are referred to as R-square (Hair et al., 2016; Naala et al., 2017; Ramayah et al., 2018). It has been posited by Falk and Miller (1992) that 0.10 is the minimum acceptable value for R-square. It was asserted by Chin (1998) that the value of R-square is strong, moderate, and weak when it is equal to 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 respectively.

Table 6: R-Square

	R Square
TECHIN	0.821
TP	0.343

Figure 3: Blindfoldings

The predictive relevance test of Stone-Geisser value (Q^2) has been performed through the use of the blindfolding processes (Hair et al., 2016; Henseler et al., 2016; Ong & Puteh, 2017). The value of Q^2 should be positive to ensure the predictive relevance of the model.

Table 7: Q-Square

	SSO	SSE	$Q^2 (=1-SSE/SSO)$
DGM	1085.000	1085.000	
TECHIN	1736.000	649.198	0.626
TP	2170.000	1644.797	0.242

5.0. Discussion and Conclusion

The consumer behavior is affected by the volume and valence of online reviews (Nusair, 2020). The quantity of reviews that are present on an online forum are considered as Volume; whereas, the rating of these online placed reviews is considered as Valence (Park, Lee, & Nicolau, 2020). Consumers consult to the online reviews for higher degree of awareness and to seek a good experience related to tourism (Gao, Gallivan, & Gong, 2020; Jiang, Chen, & Xu, 2021). The tourism industry rating is also affected by the valence of online reviews. Li and Law (2020) suggest that if there is an improvement of 10% in the rating of the reviews on the online forum, it would result in the rise of sale up to 4.4%. Dias, Silva, and Rodríguez (2020) found out that a 1-percent expansion in a tourism's online standing score paves the way to a 0.89-percent increment in cost, to a room occupancy increment of up to 0.54 percent, and to a 1.42-percent increment in RevPar. Sharma and Nayak (2020) show that if there is an increase of one point in online review, it could lead to the increase in occupancy rate for about 7.5%. Sharma and Nayak (2020) and (Casais, Fernandes, & Sarmiento, 2020) put forward the findings that the valence and volume of the online reviews would result in the rise of online bookings for tourism. Park et al. (2020) explain that there is a good and significant effect of ratings on online bookings at RevPar even if we determine it without reviews. However, potential effects of reviews and volume are focused by very few studies related to RevPAR.

How tourism performance can be made better by improving Valence and Reviews of the tourism industry is the crucial question nowadays. Strategies of DGM like keenly observing the feedbacks of customers and the analyzing them (Casais et al., 2020), giving customer prompt responses (Casais et al., 2020; González & Bulchand, 2016; Pelsmacker, Tilburg, & Holthof, 2018), developing a management plan having a good credibility (Pelsmacker et al., 2018) keeping a good track of social media activities (Pelsmacker et al., 2018) and along with it merging the websites of third-parties with tourism sites makes the review volume and valence up to profitable margin. However, González and Bulchand (2016) give the arguments that there is dire need of finding and searching new ways which could enhance the level of review volume and valence. Moreover, it is concluded that, there would be different strategies about giving a rise to review volume and valence, depending upon the type of tourism. Park et al. (2020) discuss that the different dimensions of tourism prove to be a vital moderator for Consumer behavior. Sharma and Nayak (2020) suggest that tourism occupancy can be increased by considering some of the important factors such as linkage with a tourism chain or being a high star rated firm. However, the effect of reviews on tourism performance has been studied by a few studies by examining the moderating role of tourism characteristics. But Different studied unknown versus well-known tourism, higher versus lower-tier tourisms was highlighted by Park et al. (2020), and chain versus independent tourisms was pointed out by Banerjee and Chua (2016).

According to the theoretical background, if technological advancement is employed, it can be assisting in several functions of the organizations, such as the successful role of IT in Social media applications (Agnihotri, Dingus, & Krush, 2016). The adopter of change can become capable of having development innovations. If the tested application works, firm changes its old working methods and starts to practice new ways which would lead it to innovative environment. From observing things in this regard, firms would become capable of providing innovative products and services to their customers. For instance, earlier firms used older methods for how the orders which were taken were treated but now a new software of B2B for online inventory is used (Pagani & Pardo, 2017). Adoption of this advancement will not only help the firm but also become an integral part of supply chain. According to different studies, it is evident that, technological improvement contributes in the efficiency of the firm performance and its business operations which might include relationships between the stock and stakeholders, innovation and rise in revenues. Besides the fruitful advantages of technological innovation and advancement adopted by a firm, there are also some difficulties and challenges faced by the organization in terms of consumer reactions and rival reactions. Thus, this argument reflects that the economic gains obtained by the stakeholders are inter-linked and are widely dependent upon B2B platform technological innovation (Pagani & Pardo, 2017). Relating to this perspective, there could be a higher profit and better performance outcomes generated from new ways of supply management and outward shift of older supply action, although these are obtained by vast set of mechanisms just like adopting a new and advanced technology. These evidences show that innovation related to technology is a crucial part of B2B system which

will be a key to better and higher sales (Agnihotri et al., 2016). The basic objective of this study is to examine the role of ethical leadership affecting the mechanism of technological innovation and organization's performance.

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